

High temperature oxidation behavior of AISI441 stainless steel and PDC coatings in synthetic air atmosphere

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ABSTRACT

This work features the oxidation behaviour of ferritic stainless steel grade AISI 441 coated with protective polymer derived ceramic coatings (PDC). Two PDC layers were studied with respect to their oxidation resistance in the atmosphere of synthetic air at temperatures of up to 1000 °C. The coatings contain three passive fillers: yttria-stabilized zirconia (8-YSZ, Inframat, USA), alumina-yttria-zirconia (AYZ) powder prepared via Pechini sol-gel route, and the commercial seal glass (G018-281, Schott AG). The process began with a pre-treatment of the steel substrates using ultrasonication in acetone and the preparation of the coating slurry. Subsequently, the perhydropolysilazane-based bond coat was applied via dip-coating and fixed by pyrolysis at 450 °C before the composite top coat was spray-coated and again pyrolysed in air at 850 °C. The top coats were prepared from the commercial polymer - Durazane1800 (Merck KGaA, Germany), passive fillers and commercial glass. The details of the coatings selected for oxidation testing are summarized in Tab. 1. Next, oxidation tests were performed in a horizontal electric tube furnace at 900, 950 and 1000 °C with exposure times of 24 h and 96 h in flowing synthetic air. The oxidation behaviour was evaluated by weight change measurements, which compare the mass change of coated and uncoated substrates (Tab. 2). The degree of corrosion was also investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a JEOL JSM 7600 F (JEOL, Japan).

Tab. 1: Compositions of the produced coatings before pyrolysis (vol. %) and their estimated thermal expansion coefficients (CTE, 10⁻⁶/K)

Composition	Durazane1800	YSZ	AYZ	G018-281	CTE
C2	30	35	-	35	10.1
D4	30	1.5	17.5	35	9.4

A significant weight gain of the unprotected steel was measured after all experiments due to the oxide scale growth on its surface. The small weight loss observed from the C2-coated steel after 24 h and 96 h at 900 °C can be attributed to an error in weight measurement (the total weight change is <10 mg). This also applies for the negligible weight losses measured for the D4 coated steels exposed for 24 h at 900 °C and 950 °C. After exposures to oxidative atmosphere at 950 °C and 1000 °C, the C2-coated steels showed a dramatic increase of the weight loss, indicating the total coating failure, while oxidation tests of the D4-coated steel showed a small weight gain after exposure at 950 °C and 1000 °C.

Tab. 2: Weight changes of stainless steel substrates and PDC coatings at different temperatures and times after oxidation tests (mg/cm²)

		900 °C	950 °C	1000 °C
Uncoated steel	24 h	0.21	0.44	0.72
	96 h	0.45	0.77	1.21
C2 coating	24 h	-0.11	-1.33	-4.95
	96 h	-0.14	-5.07	-5.48
D4 coating	24 h	-0.05	-0.03	0.03
	96 h	0	0.15	0.27

SEM micrograph illustrating the surface of the uncoated steel after oxidation tests at 950 °C and exposure time of 24 h is shown in Fig. 1a). The whole surface is covered with small particles of oxidation products, which were detected by XRD and EDS to be $(\text{Mn, Cr})_3\text{O}_4$ spinel, Cr_2O_3 and TiO_2 . Cross-sections of the protective coatings C2 and D4 after exposure to 950 °C for 24 h are presented by the SEM-micrographs in Fig. 1b), c). In the case of C2 coating, exposure time of 24 h to 950 °C led to progressive cracking along the metal/coating interface (marked with white arrows in Fig. 1b). Long exposure to 950 °C and 1000 °C led to an entire coating delamination, as indicated by abrupt increase in the weight loss.

The optimised composite coating D4 yielded the most promising results after oxidation tests. The D4 coating exhibited lower porosity than C2 coating. Moreover, no continuous cracks across the coating were detected. No significant corrosion damage was observed in D4 coating after oxidation tests: the coating acts as the robust oxidation protection system. This indicates that specially tailored AYZ passive filler with an adjusted CTE ensured its compatibility with the composite ceramic coating with respect to its thermal properties. Suppression of crack formation during oxidation testing was thus achieved.

Fig. 1: SEM micrographs of samples exposed to oxidation at 950 °C for 24h: a) uncoated steel surface, b) C2 cross section, c) D4 cross section

Keywords: high-temperature oxidation, PDC coatings, stainless steel

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